

COMPUTATIONAL SCIENCE GUIDED SOFT COMPUTING BASED CRYPTOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE USING ANT COLONY INTELLIGENCE FOR WIRELESS COMMUNICATION (ACICT)

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a computational science guided soft computing based cryptographic technique using Ant Colony Intelligence (ACICT) has been proposed. In this proposed approach at first a metamorphosed based strategy is used to produce intermediate cipher text. Finally, ACI generated keystream is used to further encrypt the intermediate cipher text to produce the final cipher text. In this approach an ant agent having a pheromone deposition consisting of a group of alphanumeric characters is called a key stream and each character in the key stream is known as key. The key stream length always be less than or equal to the plaintext to be encrypt. The keystream generation is based on distribution of characters in the plaintext. Instead of transmitting the plain keystream to the receiver, further encryption is done on keystream and encrypted keystream get transmitted to the receiver. Parametric tests are done and results are compared with some existing classical techniques, which show comparable results for the proposed system.

KEYWORDS

Ant Colony Intelligence (ACI), Key Generation, cryptography, soft computing

1.INTRODUCTION

These days a variety of techniques are available to secure data and information from eavesdroppers [1, 6, 7, 8, 10] with some merits and demerits. Most of the cryptographic algorithm needs large memory and energy [2, 3, 4, 5, 9]. There are few applications where soft computing is used in encryption/decryption purpose. In recent days cryptographic protocols are also get deployed in wireless communication. Wireless devices have the problem of memory and energy constraints. In this paper, a novel soft computing based technique has been proposed for encryption/decryption in wireless communication to address this problem.

The organization of this paper is as follows. Section 2 of the paper deals with the proposed ACI based key generation technique. Encryption and Decryption Process has been discussed in section 3 and 4 respectively. Example of ACI based key stream generation is discussed in section 5. Results are described in section 6. Conclusions are drawn in section 7 and that of references at end.

2. THE ACI BASED SESSION KEY GENERATION TECHNIQUE

The key stream generation process using ACI technique is illustrated using the following steps:

Step 1. In ACI based approach an ant agent is used to denote a key stream (collection of alphanumeric characters). Each Ant can have multiple dimensions. Each dimension denotes an individual key within that key stream. The dimensions in the key stream can be filled or unfilled. For example if the ceiling of dimension of each Ant is equal to 192 then it is represented by Ant_i or $Key\ stream_i = (Key_1, Key_2, \dots, Key_{192})$.

Which actually signify a key stream comprises of 192 keys i.e. 192 alphanumeric characters. Key stream length can be obtained by counting number of dimensions are filled in the key stream. Generally key stream length is less than or equal to the plain text. With 192 alphanumeric characters multiple key stream can be generated of predetermined fixed length by permutation of these predetermined fixed length characters ordering all feasible ways without any reappearance. So, for example if total number of alphanumeric characters = 192.

If key stream length = 128 then among 192 alphanumeric characters 128 alphanumeric characters are elected such a way so that by ordering all possible ways without any duplication these 128 characters forms multiple key stream having fixed length i.e. 128. For an example if 5 characters A, C, M, H, R are taken to form key stream of length 4 among 192 alphanumeric characters. Then there are 120 possible ways of obtaining key stream.

ACMHR, CAMHR, MACHR, HACMR, RACMH
ACMRH, CAMRH, MACRH, HACRM, RACHM
ACHMR, CAHMR, MAHCR, HAMCR, RAMCH
ACHRM, CAHRM, MAHRC, HAMRC, RAMHC
ACRMH, CARMH, MARCH, HARCM, RAHCM
ACRHM, CARHM, MARHC, HARMC, RAHMC
AMCHR, CMAHR, MCAHR, HCAMR, RCAMH
AMCRH, CMARH, MCAHR, HCARM, RCAHM
AMHCR, CMHAR, MCHAR, HCMAR, RCMAH
AMHRC, CMHRA, MCHRA, HCMRA, RCMHA
AMRCH, CMRAH, MCRAH, HCRAM, RCHAM
AMRHC, CMRHA, MCRHA, HCRMA, RCHMA
AHCMR, CHMRA, MHACR, HMACR, RMACH
AHCRM, CHMAR, MHARC, HMARC, RMAHC
AHMCR, CHRMA, MHCAR, HMCAR, RMCAH
AHMRC, CHRAM, MHCRA, HMCRA, RMCHA
AHRCM, CHAMR, MHRAC, HMRAC, RMHAC
AHRMC, CHARM, MHRCA, HMRCA, RMHCA

ARCMH, CRAMH, MRACH, HRACM, RHACM
 ARCHM, CRAHM, MRAHC, HRAMC, RHAMC
 ARMCH, CRMAH, MRCAH, HRCAM, RHCAM
 ARMHC, CRMHA, MRCHA, HRCMA, RHCMA
 ARHCM, CRHAM, MRHAC, HRMAC, RHMCA
 ARHMC, CRHMA, MRHCA, HRMCA, RHMCA

Using 192 characters total number of generated possible key stream is given in following equation.

$$\sum_{c=1}^{192} 192 ! / (192 - c)! \approx 192 ! (e) \approx 192 ! * 2.718$$

Step 2. According to Ant Colony Intelligence technique each ant should have an allied energy. The ACI technique also offers energy for each and every ant or key stream. The energy value of the ant agent is computed by taking the number of characters in the key stream occurring in the plain text divided by the key stream length. The pheromone deposition of the ant agent with a maximum energy value greater than a specified threshold value is the solution and the key stream is chosen for encryption. Energy value for each ant agent is computed by the following equation.

$$\text{Energy}(Ant_i) = \text{count}(key_j \in \text{plain text}) / \text{lengthof}(Ant_i),$$

where j=1, 2, ..., lengthof(Ant_i).

Step 3. *If (Energy(Ant_i) > threshold value) then
 return (Ant_i with Energy(Ant_i) = max energy value)*

Step 4. *If (Energy(Ant_i) < threshold value) then
 repeat change the key stream i.e. update the pheromone deposition of ant agent and
 perform the following steps*

Step4.1. Evaluate Energy value for each ant agent in the current trial.

Step4.1. Select the ant agent where,
*Energy(Ant_i in current trial) > threshold value) then
 return (Ant_i in current trial with Energy(Ant_i) = max energy value in current trial)
 until Energy(Ant_i in a trial) > threshold value)*

3. ENCRYPTION TECHNIQUE

Step 1. If the length of the plain text is more than length of the key stream then the values of the key stream are added to a preset value to produce the keys for the characters in the level 2 encoded plain text which is at a position greater than the length of the key stream. Predetermined value is calculated using the following equation

$$Predetermined_value = lengthof(plaintext)/2$$

Step 2. For the very first plain text block keys are form by the values of the characters in the key stream.

Step 3. For the consecutive plain text blocks keys are generated by adding preset value with the keys of the previous block for sinking the key storage load that in turn reduces the space complexity.

$$Keyforblock(i) = Keyforblock(i-1) + Predetermined_value, \text{ where } i \geq 2$$

Step 5. Now, those characters in the key stream are appearing in the plain text represent them using their corresponding ASCII code value and those characters are not appearing in the plain text represent them using their corresponding ASCII value. Then perform XOR operation between plain text and key stream to generate the encrypted cipher text.

4. DECRYPTION TECHNIQUE

Step 1. Receive the cipher text from the sender.

Step 2. Compute the predetermined value based on cipher text length.

Step 3. Using predetermined value and keys in the key stream receiver generates the keys for the portion of the text exceeding the length of the key stream.

Step 4. Generate plain text by performing XOR operation between encoded cipher text and key stream.

5. EXAMPLE OF ACI BASED KEY STREAM GENERATION

Consider the text to be encrypted is “antcolonyintelligence” threshold value is assumed to be 0.65. Each ant agent has a pheromone deposition comprising of characters representing the keystream. The energy level of the ant agent is a count of the characters in the key stream occurring in the plain text divided by the length of the keystream. The ant agent with a maximum energy level greater than the specified threshold value is chosen as the keystream for text encryption. Table. 1 shows the pheromone deposition of ant agents denoting the keystream and their corresponding energy value. Since the second ant agent in Trial II has the maximum energy value 0.66 which is greater than the threshold value. The keystream ueigunscaoblyt corresponding to that ant agent is chosen for encryption. Each character in the keystream is chosen as the key for encryption

Table 1.Pheromone deposition table

Iteration I	Energy	Iteration II	Energy
ckyaptseifdorgq	0.46	cyusadkleownjgm	0.53
anwghqbcletzduo	0.53	ueigunscaoblyt	0.66
yurtdfbnczfsvam	0.33	tedcbkhousxvaq	0.40
rqewcalkygtxifo	0.60	ivbjtwaxrdgnzpu	0.33
Highest energy	0.60	Highest energy	0.66

5.1 EXAMPLE OF CHARACTER TREE GENERATION

A character tree is generated for the plain text “antcolonyintelligence”. For plain text “antcolonyintelligence” figure 5 shows corresponding tree. Characters ‘a’, ‘y’ and ‘g’ occur once and character ‘t’, ‘c’, ‘o’ and ‘i’ occurs twice. Characters ‘l’ and ‘e’ occurs thrice. Character ‘n’ occurs four times. Each character code can be generated by preorder traversal. Left and right branches of the tree are labeled as ‘0’ and ‘1’ respectively. Table 2 depicts the code value of a particular character.

Figure 1: Character code tree

If (Code_Tree_value (Char) ==0) **then** Value(Char)= ASCII(Char) + ASCII (Code_Tree_value (Char));

If Code_Tree_value (Char) < 32 **then** Value(Char)= ASCII(Char) + Code_Tree_value (Char);

If Code_Tree_value (Char) >255 **then** Value(Char)= 255- Position_of_even_or_odd_number_series(sum_of_digit(Code_Tree_value (Char))) - number_of_1's_in (Code_Tree_value (Char));

Table 2.Code Tree table

Plain text	Code	Value	Modified value
g	0	0	$103 + 48 = 151$
e	10	2	$110 + 2 = 112$
i	110	6	$105 + 6 = 111$
y	1110	14	$117 + 14 = 128$
l	11110	30	$112 + 30 = 142$
o	111110	62	62
c	1111110	126	126
t	11111110	254	254
n	111111110	510	$255 - 3 - 8 = 244$
a	1111111110	1022	$255 - 3 - 9 = 243$

5.2.EXAMPLE OF METAMORPHOSED TREE BASED ENCRYPTION TECHNIQUE

From the original tree metamorphosed tree is derived using mutation. Table 3 depicts the metamorphosed code value. For identical entry in a table, length of the corresponding code is summed up to the character.

Figure 2: Metamorphosed Code Tree

Table 3. Metamorphosed Code Table

Plain text	Code	Value	Modified Value
g	0	0	$103 + 48 = 151$
e	11	3	$101 + 3 = 104$
i	101	5	$105 + 5 = 110$
y	1000	8	$121 + 8 = 129$
l	10010	18	$108 + 18 = 126$
o	100111	39	39
c	1001100	76	76
t	10011011	155	155
n	100110100	308	$255 - 6 - 4 = 244$
a	100110101	309	$255 - 6 - 5 = 243$

Now, the plaintext “**antcolonyintelligence**” becomes

10010111/01101000/01101110/10000001/01111110/00100111/01001100/10011011/11110100/1110011

5.3 EXAMPLE OF ANT COLONY INTELLIGENCE (ACI) KEY STREAM BASED ENCRYPTION

Now, those characters in the key stream are appearing in the plain text represent them using their corresponding character code value and those characters are not appearing in the plain text represent them using their corresponding ASCII value.

Table 4.ACC based key stream guided Encrypted text Generation Table

ACI based key stream	Blocks based on ACI based key stream Length	Value of the ACI based keys	Metamorphosed Encoded Cipher text Value	ACI based key stream
u	Block1	117 (ASCII code)	243	134
e		112 (Character code)	244	132
i		111 (Character code)	155	244
g		151 (Character code)	76	219
u		117 (ASCII code)	39	82
n		244 (Character code)	126	138
s		115 (ASCII code)	39	84
c		126 (Character code)	244	138

a		243 (Character code)	129	114
o		62 (Character code)	110	80
b		98 (ASCII code)	244	150
l		142 (Character code)	155	21
y		128 (Character code)	104	232
t		254 (Character code)	126	128
u	Block2	117 (ASCII code) + 2 (Predefine value) =119	126	9
e		112 (Character code)) + 2 (Predefine value) = 114	110	28
i		111 (Character code) + 2 (Predefine value) = 113	151	230
g		151 (Character code) + 2 (Predefine value) = 153	104	241
u		117 (ASCII code) + 2 (Predefine value) = 119	244	131
n		244 (Character code) + 2 (Predefine value) = 246	76	186
s		115 (ASCII code) + 2 (Predefine value) = 117	104	29

So, ACI encoded cipher text is

10000110/10000100/11110100/11011011/01010010/10001010/01010100/10001010
01110010/01010000/10010110/00010101/11101000/10000000/00001001/0001110011100110/11
110001/10000011/10111010/00011101

6. RESULTS

For the purpose of the practical implementation, ACICT technique has also been implemented on *SYS*, *COM*, *EXE*, *DLL*, and *CPP* files.

6.1 RESULT OF ENCRYPTION, DECRYPTION, CHI-SQUARE, DEGREE OF FREEDOM

Table 5.Result for Encryption, Decryption, Chi-Square, Degree of Freedom

Source File	Encrypted File	Source Size (In Bytes)	Encryption Time (In Seconds)	Decryption Time (In Seconds)	Chi-Square Value	Degree of Freedom
ASPI2HLP.SYS	A1.SYS	1105	0.0087	0.0083	178	171

DBLBUFF.SYS	A2.SYS	2614	0.0213	0.0206	536	234
IFSHLP.SYS	A3.SYS	3708	0.0306	0.0302	1057	239
REDBOOK.SYS	A4.SYS	5664	0.0603	0.0594	1927	246
RAMDRIVE.SYS	A5.SYS	12663	0.1362	0.1358	1429	253
CHOICE.COM	A1.COM	5239	0.0436	0.0432	1232	237
MORE.COM	A2.COM	10471	0.0873	0.0865	753	236
THELP.COM	A3.COM	11072	0.0930	0.0927	2572	252
DOSKEY.COM	A4.COM	15495	0.1671	0.163	4128	254
SYS.COM	A5.COM	18967	0.2047	0.2044	3156	255
TCDEF.EXE	A6.EXE	11611	0.0975	0.0972	3798	255
CLIPBRD.EXE	A10.EXE	18432	0.1542	0.1537	4973	255
UNZIP.EXE	A3.EXE	23044	0.1930	0.1926	2247	255
PING.EXE	A8.EXE	24576	0.2651	0.2647	4338	251
NETSTAT.EXE	A9.EXE	32768	0.3535	0.3532	8739	255
HIDCI.DLL	A1.DLL	3216	0.0262	0.0254	877	225
NDDENB.DLL	A2.DLL	10976	0.0917	0.0911	8273	253
NDDEAPI.DLL	A3.DLL	14032	0.1178	0.1173	4705	251
ICCCODES.DLL	A4.DLL	20992	0.2262	0.2253	9712	254
WINSOCK.DLL	A5.DLL	21504	0.2320	0.2314	9653	254
GRADE.CPP	A1.CPP	1257	0.0102	0.0096	442	71
MAX.CPP	A2.CPP	4071	0.0340	0.0336	2389	79
LCM.CPP	A3.CPP	4663	0.0386	0.0381	2637	88
LINEAR.CPP	A4.CPP	9540	0.1030	0.1025	13517	83
BUBBLE.CPP	A5.CPP	9558	0.1031	0.1027	14169	83

6.2 RESULT FOR FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION TESTS

The frequency of each of the 255 characters in the source file and the same in the encrypted file were calculated and compared to assess the efficiency of the proposed technique.

Figure 3. Segment of Frequency Distribution Chart for .SYS File

6.3 KEY STORAGE COMPARISON AND ANALYSIS WITH EXISTING METHODS

Table 7 shows the comparison results among ACICT, AES, RC4 and Vernam Cipher.

Table 6
Comparison of key storage in Proposed ACICT, AES, RC4 and Vernam Cipher

Length of Plain text	Key Storage (ACICT)	Key Storage (AES)	Key Storage (RC4)	Key Storage (Vernam Cipher)
64	15	128	52	60
120	15	128	106	120
500	15	128	437	500
1000	20	128	913	1000

In ACICT only 15 bits key stream need to be store for plain text size 64, 120 500 and for the plain text of length 1000 only 20 bits key stream need to be store. In ACICT If the key stream size is less than the plain text to be encrypt then the key stream can be expand by summing up a fixed value with the existing key stream for the plain text grater than the key stream in terms of length.

Figure 4: Memory heap

The figure 4 shows the memory heap usage for at the run time.

Figure 5: Memory Gantt Chart

Figure 5 shows Memory Gantt Chart during execution.

Figure 6: Number of Threads at runtime

Figure 6 shows the various numbers of threads active during runtime.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper an Ant Colony Intelligence algorithm to generate the key stream for encryption based on the distribution of characters in the plain text has been proposed. In this method the pheromone deposition of the ant agent evaporates when it moves to the next trail and therefore the ant agent needs to update the pheromone deposition representing the key stream. The energy value denoting its attractiveness towards the solution is found by counting the number of characters in the key stream occurring in the plain text. In future other soft computing tools can be applied in cryptographic domain.

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References

- [1] Atul Kahate, Cryptography and Network Security, 2003, Tata McGraw-Hill publishing Company Limited, Eighth reprint 2006.
- [2] R. Mislovaty, Y. Perchenok, I. Kanter, and W. Kinzel. Secure key-exchange protocol with an absence of injective functions. Phys. Rev. E, 66:066102, 2002.
- [3] A. Ruttor, W. Kinzel, R. Naeh, and I. Kanter. Genetic attack on neural cryptography. Phys. Rev. E, 73(3):036121, 2006.
- [4] Wolfgang Kinzel and Ido Kanter, "Neural cryptography" proceedings of the 9th international conference on Neural Information processing(ICONIP 03).
- [5] Charles Pfleeger, Shari Lawrence Pfleeger, Security in computing, Third Edition 2003, pp 48, Prentice Hall of India Pvt Ltd, New Delhi.
- [6] Biham, E. and Seberry, J."Py (Roo): A Fast and Secure Stream Cipher". EUROCRYPT'05 Rump Session, at the Symmetric Key Encryption Workshop (SKEW 2005), 26-27 May 2005.
- [7] Chung-Ping Wu, C.C. Jay Kuo, "Design of Integrated Multimedia Compression and Encryption Systems", IEEE Transactions on Multimedia, Volume 7, Issue 5, Oct. 2005 Page(s): 828 – 839.
- [8] HongGeun Kim, JungKyu Han and Seongje Cho."An efficient implementation of RC4 cipher for encrypting multimedia files on mobile devices". SAC '07 Proceedings of the ACM symposium on Applied computing, 2007, pp 1171--1175, NewYork, USA.
- [9] Mantin and A. Shamir, "Weaknesses in the key scheduling algorithm of RC4", Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 2259, Revised Papers from the 8th Annual International Workshop on Selected Areas in Cryptography, pp: 1 - 24, 2007.
- [10] Sarkar Arindam, Mandal J. K., "Artificial Neural Network Guided Secured Communication Techniques: A Practical Approach", Paperback: 128 pages, Publisher: LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing (June 4, 2012), Language: English, ISBN-10: 3659119911, ISBN-13: 978-3659119910.

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